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Dalit Micro-level Entrepreneurs at Outskirt: Some Experiences from the Field

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Abstract A Dalit micro-level entrepreneur is a Dalit person who starts up, organizes, manages, and controls their occupation with all risks and rewards. Dalits in India were economically depreciated and excluded from entrepreneurship due to the Caste system. They were discriminated against, exploited, and excluded from the mainstream of every field in the past. As per the Report of Micro, Small, and medium enterprises (MSME), Dalit-owned occupations are below average in India. The main objective of the present research paper is to study the various challenges faced by Dalit micro-level entrepreneurs in their occupations. The researcher took a sample of 100 Dalit micro-level entrepreneurs by Purposive Representative Sampling Technique. The present research is quantitative and descriptive in nature. For the analysis of data, the researcher has used mixed method techniques. The researcher used statistical techniques for the quantitative analysis of the data, and thematic formation techniques to analyze the qualitative data. Dalit entrepreneurs can be planned and developed and the need for providing appropriate awareness and environment to promote entrepreneurship is of vital importance. This research paper focused on some experiences from the field of Dalit micro-level entrepreneurs in Delhi.

Keywords Dalit, Micro Level, Entrepreneurs, Outskirt.

Introduction

This research paper provides a panoramic thought process of the entrepreneurial background of the Dalit micro-level entrepreneurs. It elaborates on the types and nature of micro-entrepreneurship like general stores, leather-related work, vegetable -shops, small food stalls, stationery and other accessories Shops, mobile accessories, fruit shops, chemist shops, etc. of the respondents. This section focuses on the issues and challenges of the respondents concerning start-up entrepreneurship, encouragement and motivational factors, financial issues, managing and organizing entrepreneurship, etc. In line with this, Julija (2013), Anupam (2014), Anis, & Yasir (2014), Sabharwal (2011), Paul, Burns (2001), Bhatt, M. A. (2015), and Kamble, Milind. (2005) pinpointed the term, 'Entrepreneurship', various types of entrepreneurs, and emerging issues & challenges in their studies. Pokharel and Dhundi Raj (2010) revealed the Dalit entrepreneurship working style and their limited credit sources. He stated that most Dalits are unskilled therefore they are not capable of transforming their traditional businesses into modern businesses. Due to their poor background, they have no collateral assets for taking loans.

Objective of study To discuss some field experiences of Dalit micro-level Entrepreneurs.

Review of Literature Yadav et al. (2021) examined the situation in Uttar Pradesh and discovered that the MSME sector, which includes handicrafts, experienced an alarming income decline of over 70%. The demonetization initiative implemented by the Union Government in 2016 led to a complete breakdown of working capital and cash flow within the micro, small, and medium enterprises, and just as recovery was beginning to take shape, the effects of COVID-19 worsened the circumstances (Yadav et al., 2021:2). According to Nag (2022), "The cottage industrial sector has been a significant concern for a long time, yet minimal efforts have been made to foster its inclusive growth in recent years. India is positioned 68th out of 141 on the Global Competitiveness Index (GCI), having numerous small-scale industries (SSI) and cottage enterprises but lacking adequate regulations, funding, and infrastructure to support them. While the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) have established a foundation for improvement, their implementation remains significantly lacking. Cottage industries serve as the cornerstone of rural communities and offer considerable job creation potential; thus, locally sourced

SSI may possess a sustainable development advantage compared to imported SSI (Nag:204).”

According to Nag (2023), “Rural cottage industries in India have provided a crucial income source for non-farming communities, but they have faced challenges in partnering with the government and businesses to achieve the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). One such challenge is the insufficient support for micro, small, and medium enterprises (MSMEs) in their active pursuit of sustainability, which could be improved by enhancing sustainability measures and providing capacity-building opportunities. The roles of supply chain and community stakeholders in building sector infrastructure are often underestimated. Bishnupur is similarly experiencing a loss of skilled artisans due to urban migration and low wages. They lack infrastructure and financial resources (Nag,2023:471).”

Bruntha & Subaithani (2024) examine the roles and challenges in the growth of village and cottage industries, emphasizing their significance in generating employment, preserving traditional skills, promoting rural development, and adopting sustainable practices. They highlight the challenges these industries face, including inadequate infrastructure, limited financing options, difficulties in accessing markets and marketing, the need for skill development and training, and competition from large-scale production. They also address these hurdles, and village & cottage industries can flourish, supporting sustainable economic progress while preserving cultural heritage (Bruntha & Subaithani, 2024).

Methodology

The present research paper is based on a survey technique in which the researcher used the mixed method technique. Research Design helps the researcher to develop an understanding of the conceptual and theoretical perspective with more crops by selecting a sequestrate methodology. This research paper puts forward the monumental work through which objectives is achieved. It also moves out to the research objective, the research design used by the researcher to collect the data from the field. The selected research is survey research. In this disquiet, Cohen et. (2000) have described the survey research in the following approach: “Surveys gather data at a particular point in time to describe the nature of existing conditions or identify standards against which existing conditions can be compared ordetermine the relationships that exist between specific events. Thus, their levels of complexity may vary from those which provide simple frequency counts to those which present relational analysis “. (Cohen et.al, 2000:169). For the data analysis, the researcher has used mixed method techniques. For the analysis of qualitative data, the investigator has used thematic formation techniques. For quantitative analysis of data, the researcher has used statistical techniques in which data has been presented in bar diagrams and pie diagrams.

Tools Used For the fieldwork/data collection structured questionnaire has been used for respondents, in which 12 questions were developed related to the issues and challenges faced by the Dalit micro-level entrepreneurs. This selected research has been conducted in the National Capital Territory of Delhi.

Analysis

Historically in India society was divided according to the Verna Such as Brahmin, Kshatriya, Vaishya, and Shudra. Traditionally as per Verna occupation was assigned accordingly and entrepreneurship has been dominated largely by the Vaishya Verna such as Baniya, Khatri, and Arora. Besides this some regional communities such as Marwaris, Sindhi, Punjabi, and Gujarati and some family businesses (Judge and Bal: 2009:150). Traditionally there was a restriction to breaking the ceiling of Verna's, community, and family occupations. In line with this, Ghurye (1969) stated that there is an association between caste and occupation in India but now there is no such type of ceiling in the context of vernacular occupations. In this section, the researcher discussed the entrepreneurship and social background of the respondents. This section is based on the two components such as entrepreneurship. The first component is related to the various elements included such as respondent's business was a hereditary occupation or not, how many generations are involved, who started their entrepreneurship, and their challenges towards their entrepreneurship. The second component depends upon the social background of the entrepreneurs and the effect of social profiles such as caste, religion, etc. social networking on their entrepreneurship.

Diagram No. 1.1 Types of Business

Diagram no. 1.1 Pinpoints the various types of businesses operated by the respondents. The present Diagram shows that 30% of respondents were running general stores. 36% of respondents were doing leather related. As per the diagram, 10% of respondents were running vegetable shops. 6% of respondents were running small food stalls and the same number of respondents were running stationary and other accessories shops. If these data are presented with critical appraisal, the majority of the respondents (76%) were involved in a few occupations (Leathers related work, General Stores, Vegetable Shops, etc.) and the remaining 24 % of respondents were engaged in other occupations such as Fruit Shops, Mobile Accessories etc. As per the data shown in the present table, the researcher didn't find any entrepreneur who was involved in jewelry, making business, or outlets to sell electrical items.

Diagram 1.2: Time Spam for Start-up Entrepreneurship

Diagram no. 1.2 reveals the entrepreneurship start-up of the respondents before the GST Act 2017 and after the implementation of the GST Act 2017. The data shown in the present table represents that 96% of respondents started their entrepreneurship before the implementation of the GST, Act. 2017. Only 4 % of respondents started their entrepreneurship after the implementation of the GST.

Diagram No.1.3: Encouraged Factors to Start this Entrepreneurship

Diagram 1.3 provides data about the motivational and encouragement factors to start entrepreneurship among the respondents. The data shown in the present diagram states that 62 % of respondents were self-motivated to start their entrepreneurship 28% of respondents were motivated and encouraged by their parents to begin their businesses. 6% of respondents were encouraged by their spouses. The remaining 4% of respondents were motivated and encouraged by other components such as relatives and friends etc. In brief, the data shown in the present table states that most of the respondents (90%) were self-motivated and encouraged by themselves and then motivated by their parents.

Diagram No.1.4: Financial Problems Faced by Entrepreneurs

Diagram No. 1.4 Explains the problems related to the financial aspect of the informants. The current diagram clarifies that 78 % of the informants have financial issues to start up their cottage-scale entrepreneurship. Present data also reveals that only 22% of respondents had no financial issues to start their entrepreneurship and during the entrepreneurship. In conclusion, most entrepreneurs have faced financial problems starting the present cottage-scale entrepreneurship.

Diagram no. 1.5: Kinds of Problems Faced by the Entrepreneurs

Diagram No. 1.5 explains the various types of problems faced by entrepreneurs. The data shown in the present diagram explains that 34 % of respondents have a shortage of Capital. 8% of entrepreneurs lack space to run their businesses successfully. Besides these problems, data also marked some other problems, such as lack of education (12%)

among respondents, 24% of respondents were affected by their Dalit caste background. Many respondents (6%) faced market-related problems. In the present diagram, the data shows that the major problems faced by entrepreneurs were lack of education, and caste-related issues, and the bigger problem faced by the respondents was the lack of capital available for the business. They still belonged to the marginalized group.

Diagram No. 1.6: Head of the business

Diagram No. 1.6 represents the head or owner of the entrepreneurship. The data mentioned in this diagram states that 82 % of respondents were the head and governed their entrepreneurship by themselves. The entrepreneurship of 10% of respondents is managed, controlled, and headed by their parents. The entrepreneurship of 2% of respondents was encouraged by their husbands. The entrepreneurship of 2% of respondents (5 respondents) was managed, controlled, and headed by their brothers. The entrepreneurship of the remaining 4% of respondents is managed, controlled, and headed by others. In general, this diagram states that the entrepreneurship of the majority of respondents (92% of respondents) was controlled and headed either by themselves or their parents.

Diagram no. 1.7: Financial Aid from the government

Diagram no. 1.7 provides the data about the financial assistance or financial aid taken by the respondents from the government. The responses shown in the present diagram pinpoints that 86 % of respondents did not take any financial aid from the Government to start their entrepreneurship due to various issues during their entrepreneurship. Only 14 % of respondents took financial aid from the Government to start their entrepreneurship and during their entrepreneurship. The data shown in the present diagram states that the larger part of informants did not benefit from any type of financial assistance to start their entrepreneurship and during their entrepreneurship.

B.1: Types of Government and Private Aids:

When the researcher asked to the respondents about financial aid from government agencies. The data gathered from the fieldwork clarifies that only 6 % of respondents have taken financial aid from public sector banks to start their entrepreneurship and during the entrepreneurship. The remaining 86 % of respondents have not taken any type of financial help from the Government. In general, the majority of respondents had not

taken any financial assistance. The remaining 14% of respondents have availed financial aid from various agencies of the Government to start entrepreneurship and during the entrepreneurship.

Diagram No. 1.8: Aids from the Private Agencies

Diagram no. 1.8 provides data about various types of aid availed by the respondents from the various private sector financial agencies. The present diagram presents the financial outlook of the respondents. This current diagram states that 8 % of respondents availed and managed the financial funds from private banks such as ICICI and HDFC etc. to start entrepreneurship and during entrepreneurship. This diagram also shows that 4% of respondents took financial aid (Credit) from private cooperative societies to start entrepreneurship. It was clear from the data shown in this diagram that 4% of respondents availed the loans from private sector companies, and 2 % of respondents took financial aid (Credit) from their relatives and friends to start entrepreneurship and during the entrepreneurship. In general, this diagram states that the majority of respondents (82% respondents) have not availed the financial aid from the financial agencies of the private sector due to various issues such as lack of collateral assets, the demand for bribe sanctioning loans, multiple visits, the process of lengthy documentation, etc., for the start-up of their entrepreneurship and during their entrepreneurship.

Section- C: Entrepreneurship Background of the Respondents

In this section, the researcher discussed the entrepreneurship background of the respondents. This section is based on the two components such as entrepreneurship and social background. This section is related to the various elements included such as respondent’s business was a hereditary occupation or not, how many generations are involved, who started their entrepreneurship, and their challenges towards their entrepreneurship. The researcher also discusses the effect of social profiles such as caste, religion, etc. social networking on their entrepreneurship.

Diagram No. 1.9: Family Business or Not

Diagram no. 1.9 represents the data about the entrepreneurship of the entrepreneurs as a family business or not. The data mentioned in the present diagram pinpoints that 32 % of respondents were doing family entrepreneurship. The remaining 68 % of respondents

were not involved in their family business. It means they break the ceiling of a traditional family business. The majority of respondents (68%) were not running their family entrepreneurship.

Diagram No. 1.10 Involvement of the Generations in this Business

Diagram no.1.10 represents the data about the generations holding the entrepreneurship of the respondents. It was clear that 66 % of respondents were the first generation of entrepreneurs. 28 % of respondents were doing entrepreneurship from two generations. 4 % of respondents were doing entrepreneurship for three generations, remaining 2 % of respondents were running their occupations for more than three generations mean lie in the others category. The majority of respondents were running their business from the first and second generations.

Diagram No. 1.11: Who Started this Business

Diagram no. 1.11 represents the data about starting entrepreneurship. It is clear from the responses that 66 % of respondents started their entrepreneurship by themselves. The entrepreneurship of 28 % of respondents started their entrepreneurship with other family members. The entrepreneurship of 4 % of respondents was started by their husbands. The entrepreneurship of 2% of respondents was started by their parents. In conclusion, the present diagram states that the entrepreneurship of the majority of respondents (72 % of respondents) was started either by themselves or by their parents and spouses.

Diagram No. 1.12: Impact of Caste on their Business

Diagram no. 1.12 states the impact of social background on the entrepreneurship of the respondents. The data shown in the current diagram states that 72 % of respondents acknowledge that social backgrounds such as Caste and class massively affected their entrepreneurship. The remaining 28 % of the respondents admit that their social background didn't affect their entrepreneurship directly. The rigorous fieldwork data states that the majority of the respondents, 72 % of respondents' social background (caste and religion) affected their entrepreneurship directly and only 28% of respondents' entrepreneurship was not affected due to caste and religion discrimination.

Social Networking, Basis and Its Impact on Entrepreneurship

The data reveal that 72%of respondents 28%) were gathered from partial consideration concerning. When the researcher discussed the nature and basis of social networking, they discussed many factors concerning social networking, such as:

1. Social background based on caste.
2. Economic background based on financial conditions and class.
3. Educational background.
4. Relationship with other entrepreneurs.
5. Effective use of Information Communication & Technology (ICT).
6. Communication skills.

In the entire discussion process about the impact of social networking, mainly two crucial factors have emerged. Firstly, social background includes caste, class and creed. Secondly, the level of education of the entrepreneurs. Both the components were determined factors for favorable outcomes of entrepreneurship.

Problem-Related to the Demand and Supply

During fieldwork for the data collection, the researcher spent almost one year of rigorous fieldwork. Beyond the questionnaire, respondents discuss many other things related to their business. There were all crucial points to assess the findings of this selected research.

Marketing Problems: About 1/5th of the entrepreneurs admits that both online and offline marketing issues occurred due to the pandemic situation, entrepreneurs faced major problems regarding the supply (sales) of their goods due to the absence of e-marketing or online marketing platforms. Most of the consumers shifted to online marketing during the pandemic period. The entrepreneurs needed extra staff for free home delivery. The offline marketing platform increases the burden of the extra cost of entrepreneurs to cope with the domination of online marketing platforms. They faced drastic losses with this problem.

High Competition in the Market: There were 100 respondents involved in the fieldwork process and certain respondents faced high competition from other fellows- entrepreneurs (Both Dalit and Non-Dalits) having long-term experience in a similar field. Most of the entrepreneurs were engaged in an unorganized set-up.

Inflation and Expensive Products: Generally, prices of goods and services increase continuously due to inflation in India. The data states that the larger part of the Dalit entrepreneurs faced the problem of high rice prices of commodities due to the high demand and low supply of the products during the pandemic situation and other emergency conditions.

Lack of money: Several respondents faced a drastic problem related to the availability of inadequate funds. they were not capable of getting proper loans from banks or other agencies due to the lack of collateral security and lengthy and technical procedures of documentation. Due to this problem, they were unable to achieve the target of sales and satisfactory margin.

Problem-Related to the Location: Many of the respondents faced a problem related to the poor location, where they worked or ran their businesses. Even due to the narrow space of the workplace, means of transport were unable to reach the desired destination. Due to this massive problem, entrepreneurs were unable to achieve their target of sales and purchases.

Communication Skills: As per the observation by the researcher and through the process of discussion with the respondents, almost 60% of the Dalit entrepreneurs

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hesitated during the process of the interview. Due to this problem, they have low self-confidence, low self-esteem, and fears of commuting mistakes, which affects their occupations adversely.

In concluding remarks demand and supply are the significant components for the smooth running of the business. Some of the respondents faced problems related to demand and supply such as marketing networking, lack of money, lack of communication skills, etc.

Conclusion

To achieve this objective researcher has developed many items in the questionnaire, such as types of business, time spam and encouraging factors for start-up this business, financial hurdles and issues faced by the informants, etc. The findings are as under: After analyzing the collected data, the researcher examined that the larger part of the participants (76%) was doing only three occupations such as leather-related work, Small General stores, and Vegetable shops, etc. The remaining 24 % of respondents were engaging in other occupations such as Fruits and, Juice shops, Stationery and other accessories shops, small food stalls, and chemist shops. Lastly, most of the entrepreneurs were micro-scale Dalit entrepreneurs. It is clear from the findings that none of the respondents was involved in medium and large-scale businesses. In this concern, some of the respondents were involved and running their family business only which was shifted from one generation to another. It is also clear from the data that the encouraged factors to start the business respondents were (90%) either themselves or their parents. The remaining 10% of respondents were motivated and encouraged by other factors such as spouses, relatives, and friends to begin their entrepreneurship. When the researcher asked about financial problems (if any) faced by the entrepreneurs, in this concern the data revealed that a larger number of entrepreneurs (78%) had financial issues to starting their entrepreneurship and during their entrepreneurship. The remaining 22% of entrepreneurs do not face financial issues to start entrepreneurship and during entrepreneurship. In this unsettled concern, the similar argument given by Singh, Garg, and Deshmukh, (2010:1081) discussed the various constraints of small-scale business including financial issues such as shortage of collateral securities, etc. in their research. When the researcher asked the respondents about the nature of the problems they faced during their entrepreneurship, they discussed various kinds of problems, such as shortage of capital (34%), lack of space (08%), problems related to the market (06%), lack of education (12%), social problems (based on caste) (24%), problems of demand and supply of goods (6.4%). Along with these problems entrepreneurs have faced some other problems, such as social networking, lack of information about Information technology and communication (ICT), etc. A larger number of the respondents (78%) have faced financial problems during their entrepreneurship. When the researcher discussed financial assistance for their entrepreneurship, most of the respondents (86%) didn't avail of financial help from government agencies. Another 14 % of respondents benefitted from the government agencies to start their entrepreneurship and during their entrepreneurship. Apart from this government assistance, 8% of the respondents (20) availed the financial assistance from private agencies. In this concern, "Moreover, entrepreneurial opportunities are extremely limited for Dalits as they lack both capital and the collateral to secure loans (Sesha Kethineni and Gail Diane Humiston:2010:138)". One another aspect was discussed with the respondents about the generations engaged in the present entrepreneurship. In this discussion, the concise majority of respondents (68%) were not involved in their family entrepreneurship. Only 32% of respondents (80) were doing their traditional or family businesses. It means the larger part of the respondents break the ceiling of traditional family businesses. In other words, the majority of respondents (94%) were involved with this current business by the first and second generation. The analysis of data of the present research also examined that a large number of respondents (72 %) started this entrepreneurship either by themselves or by their parents and spouses. The remaining 28 % of the entrepreneurs were started by other family members such as brothers, uncles, etc. Historically there was an association between caste and occupation in India. (Judge & Bal, 2009 and Ghurye, 1969) The present data also reveals that 72% of the respondents contemplated that social background enormously impacted their occupation. The rest of the 28% of responses were in favor of that social background didn't affect their entrepreneurship. Many determining factors affect the occupation crucially such as social, economic, educational, and information about the technology, etc. In this selected research 66% of respondents confirmed the significance of social networking for favorable outcomes of their entrepreneurship. Some other responses (34%) were gathered in partial consideration. When the researcher discussed the nature and basis of social networking, they discussed many factors concerning social networking, such as social background based on caste, educational background, economic background based on financial conditions and class, relationship with other entrepreneurs, ICT and lastly good communication skills. When the researcher asked them about the various challenges related to the demand and supply of the goods for their entrepreneurship. In this discussion researcher has received abundant responses like marketing problems, high competition in the market, inflation and expensive products, lack of money, location problems inadequate communication skills, etc. Many of the respondents admit that online as well as offline marketing occurred due to the pandemic situation. Entrepreneurs faced major problems regarding the supply of their

goods due to the absence of an e-marketing or online marketing platform. Most of the consumers shifted to online marketing platforms during the pandemic situation. They needed extra staff for free home delivery. The offline marketing platform increased the extra burden of cost on entrepreneurs to compete with the monopoly of online platforms. The entrepreneurs faced drastic losses due to this problem.

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